

REVIEW

[version 1; peer review: 1 not approved]

Digital credentials for environmental competencies: A review of open recognition systems in climate education

[version 1; peer review: 1 not approved]

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V1 **First published:** 19 May 2025, 5:138
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20048.1>
Second version: 27 Jun 2025, 5:138
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20048.2>
Latest published: 11 Aug 2025, 5:138
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20048.3>

Abstract

Open education recognition systems are transforming how skills and competencies are validated across formal, informal, and non-formal learning environments. This literature review examines current practices in open recognition, with particular emphasis on micro-credentials, digital badges, and open educational resources (OER), while specifically exploring their application and potential in climate education. The analysis reveals significant potential for these systems to bridge academic learning with professional demands and environmental action, particularly through competency-based approaches. However, persistent challenges in standardization, technological integration, and stakeholder collaboration require attention for these systems to reach their full potential. This review aligns with the OpenPass4Climate (2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000089354) Erasmus+ project's goals of fostering sustainable, inclusive education systems by synthesizing key contributions, identifying challenges, and proposing recommendations from researchers in the field. Notable findings include the growing importance of micro-credentials for validating climate adaptation skills, the value of open badges in recognizing interdisciplinary competencies essential for environmental action, and the need for integrated qualification frameworks that can accommodate both

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2
version 3 (revision) 11 Aug 2025		 view
version 2 (revision) 27 Jun 2025	 view	
version 1 19 May 2025		

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

formal and informal learning pathways in sustainability education. The review concludes by highlighting promising practices in Nordic regions where micro-credentials and open badges are being successfully employed in sustainable tourism education and climate adaptation learning networks.

Offene Anerkennungssysteme im Bildungsbereich verändern die Art und Weise, wie Fähigkeiten und Kompetenzen in formellen, informellen und non-formalen Lernumgebungen validiert werden. Diese Literaturübersicht untersucht aktuelle Praktiken der offenen Anerkennung, mit besonderem Schwerpunkt auf Micro-Credentials, digitalen Abzeichen und offenen Bildungsressourcen (OER), während sie speziell deren Anwendung und Potenzial in der Klimabildung erforscht. Die Analyse zeigt ein erhebliches Potenzial dieser Systeme, akademisches Lernen mit beruflichen Anforderungen und Umweltmaßnahmen zu verbinden, insbesondere durch kompetenzbasierte Ansätze. Jedoch erfordern anhaltende Herausforderungen bei der Standardisierung, der technologischen Integration und der Zusammenarbeit der Interessengruppen Aufmerksamkeit, damit diese Systeme ihr volles Potenzial entfalten können. Diese Übersicht steht im Einklang mit den Zielen des Erasmus+-Projekts OpenPass4Climate (2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000089354), nachhaltige und inklusive Bildungssysteme zu fördern, indem sie wichtige Beiträge zusammenfasst, Herausforderungen identifiziert und Empfehlungen von Forschern auf diesem Gebiet vorschlägt. Zu den bemerkenswerten Ergebnissen gehören die wachsende Bedeutung von Micro-Credentials für die Validierung von Klimaanpassungsfähigkeiten, der Wert offener Abzeichen bei der Anerkennung interdisziplinärer Kompetenzen, die für Umweltmaßnahmen unerlässlich sind, und die Notwendigkeit integrierter Qualifikationsrahmen, die sowohl formelle als auch informelle Lernwege in der Nachhaltigkeitsbildung berücksichtigen können. Die Übersicht schließt mit der Hervorhebung vielversprechender Praktiken in nordischen Regionen, wo Micro-Credentials und offene Abzeichen erfolgreich in der Bildung für nachhaltigen Tourismus und in Lernnetzwerken zur Klimaanpassung eingesetzt werden.

Les systèmes de reconnaissance de l'éducation ouverte transforment la façon dont les compétences sont validées dans les environnements d'apprentissage formels, informels et non formels. Cette revue de littérature examine les pratiques actuelles en matière de reconnaissance ouverte, en mettant particulièrement l'accent sur les micro-certifications, les badges numériques et les ressources éducatives libres (REL), tout en explorant spécifiquement leur application et leur potentiel dans l'éducation au climat. L'analyse révèle un potentiel significatif pour ces systèmes de faire le lien entre l'apprentissage académique, les exigences professionnelles et l'action environnementale, notamment grâce à des approches basées sur les compétences. Cependant, des défis persistants en matière de standardisation, d'intégration technologique et de collaboration entre les parties prenantes requièrent une attention particulière pour que ces systèmes atteignent leur plein potentiel. Cette revue s'aligne sur

les objectifs du projet Erasmus+ OpenPass4Climate (2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000089354) visant à favoriser des systèmes éducatifs durables et inclusifs en synthétisant les contributions clés, en identifiant les défis et en proposant des recommandations issues des chercheurs du domaine. Les résultats notables incluent l'importance croissante des micro-certifications pour valider les compétences d'adaptation au climat, la valeur des badges ouverts dans la reconnaissance des compétences interdisciplinaires essentielles à l'action environnementale, et le besoin de cadres de qualification intégrés pouvant accueillir à la fois des parcours d'apprentissage formels et informels dans l'éducation au développement durable. La revue conclut en soulignant les pratiques prometteuses dans les régions nordiques où les micro-certifications et les badges ouverts sont utilisés avec succès dans l'éducation au tourisme durable et les réseaux d'apprentissage sur l'adaptation au climat.

I sistemi di riconoscimento dell'educazione aperta stanno trasformando il modo in cui competenze e abilità vengono validate negli ambienti di apprendimento formali, informali e non formali. Questa revisione della letteratura esamina le pratiche attuali nel riconoscimento aperto, con particolare enfasi su micro-credenziali, badge digitali e risorse educative aperte (OER), esplorando specificamente la loro applicazione e potenziale nell'educazione climatica. L'analisi rivela un potenziale significativo per questi sistemi di collegare l'apprendimento accademico con le esigenze professionali e l'azione ambientale, in particolare attraverso approcci basati sulle competenze. Tuttavia, sfide persistenti nella standardizzazione, nell'integrazione tecnologica e nella collaborazione tra le parti interessate richiedono attenzione affinché questi sistemi raggiungano il loro pieno potenziale. Questa revisione si allinea con gli obiettivi del progetto Erasmus+ OpenPass4Climate (2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000089354) di promuovere sistemi educativi sostenibili e inclusivi, sintetizzando contributi chiave, identificando sfide e proponendo raccomandazioni dai ricercatori del settore. I risultati notevoli includono la crescente importanza delle micro-credenziali per la validazione delle competenze di adattamento climatico, il valore dei badge aperti nel riconoscimento delle competenze interdisciplinari essenziali per l'azione ambientale, e la necessità di quadri di qualificazione integrati che possano accogliere sia percorsi di apprendimento formali che informali nell'educazione alla sostenibilità. La revisione si conclude evidenziando pratiche promettenti nelle regioni nordiche dove micro-credenziali e badge aperti vengono impiegati con successo nell'educazione al turismo sostenibile e nelle reti di apprendimento sull'adattamento climatico.

Los sistemas de reconocimiento de la educación abierta están transformando la forma en que se validan las habilidades y competencias en entornos de aprendizaje formales, informales y no formales. Esta revisión de literatura examina las prácticas actuales en reconocimiento abierto, con particular énfasis en las microcredenenciales, insignias digitales y recursos educativos abiertos (REA), al tiempo que explora específicamente su aplicación y potencial en la educación climática. El análisis revela un potencial significativo para que estos sistemas conecten el aprendizaje académico con las demandas profesionales y la acción ambiental, particularmente a

través de enfoques basados en competencias. Sin embargo, los desafíos persistentes en estandarización, integración tecnológica y colaboración entre las partes interesadas requieren atención para que estos sistemas alcancen su pleno potencial. Esta revisión se alinea con los objetivos del proyecto Erasmus+ OpenPass4Climate (2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000089354) de fomentar sistemas educativos sostenibles e inclusivos mediante la síntesis de contribuciones clave, la identificación de desafíos y la propuesta de recomendaciones de investigadores en el campo. Los hallazgos notables incluyen la creciente importancia de las microcredenciales para validar habilidades de adaptación climática, el valor de las insignias abiertas en el reconocimiento de competencias interdisciplinarias esenciales para la acción ambiental, y la necesidad de marcos de cualificación integrados que puedan acomodar tanto vías de aprendizaje formales como informales en la educación para la sostenibilidad. La revisión concluye destacando prácticas prometedoras en las regiones nórdicas donde las microcredenciales y las insignias abiertas se están empleando con éxito en la educación turística sostenible y en redes de aprendizaje sobre adaptación climática.

Plain language summary

This review examines how digital badges and micro-credentials can be used to recognize learning and actions related to climate change. These digital recognition tools provide ways to acknowledge skills and knowledge gained outside traditional education. We analyzed research published between 2010 and 2024 to understand current practices, challenges, and recommendations.

The review found that digital badges and micro-credentials can effectively validate climate-related competencies across various learning environments. They are particularly useful for recognizing interdisciplinary skills and action-oriented achievements essential for addressing climate challenges. However, there are significant obstacles to their widespread adoption, including lack of standardization, limited awareness among employers, and technical implementation barriers.

Based on the literature, we recommend integrating these recognition systems into institutional programs, aligning them with employer needs, developing clear design standards, and creating frameworks specifically for climate education. The findings suggest that with proper implementation, digital recognition systems could bridge formal education with practical environmental actions, offering flexible pathways for developing climate literacy and action competencies.

This research is part of the OpenPass4Climate Erasmus+ project, which aims to develop an open recognition system for climate-related achievements across European higher education institutions.

Keywords

climate literacy, competency frameworks, educational innovation, environmental skills, lifelong learning, micro-credentials, open badges, education

This article is included in the [Erasmus+](#) gateway.

This article is included in the [Adaptation to Climate Change](#) collection.

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Author roles: **Martín-Ramos P:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Díaz-De-Oleo D:** Formal Analysis, Investigation; **Fourati-Jamoussi F:** Formal Analysis, Investigation; **Couchy K:** Investigation, Project Administration; **Lo Giudice LA:** Formal Analysis, Investigation; **Tosi B:** Investigation, Project Administration; **Oliveira-Pinto F:** Formal Analysis, Investigation; **Veiga-Martins L:** Investigation, Project Administration; **Navas-Gracia LM:** Investigation, Project Administration

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union through the Erasmus+ programme under grant agreement No. 2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000089354 (Impact evaluation of eco-pedagogy towards Individual and Collective Engagement through the implementation of a European Open Badges Passport for Climate and Planet [OpenPass4Climate]).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

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How to cite this article: Martín-Ramos P, Díaz-De-Oleo D, Fourati-Jamoussi F *et al.* **Digital credentials for environmental competencies: A review of open recognition systems in climate education [version 1; peer review: 1 not approved]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:138 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20048.1>

First published: 19 May 2025, 5:138 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20048.1>

Introduction

Overview of the OpenPass4Climate project

The global climate crisis demands not only awareness but meaningful commitment and action. The OpenPass4Climate (2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000089354) Erasmus+ project emerges as a response to this need. The project strives to transform climate-related educational initiatives, elevating them beyond awareness-building to foster concrete commitments to environmental action and climate justice. This transformation will be facilitated through the implementation of open recognition tools, specifically open badges integrated within the OpenPass4Climate digital platform. The project seeks to assess the tangible impact of these activities on driving real changes for climate justice and to understand the mechanisms that facilitate the rapid replication of positive behaviors in environmental contexts.

The implementation strategy encompasses a range of activities, from mapping eco-pedagogical initiatives to evaluating achievements through an Open Recognition System (ORS). The project actively advocates for a European vision, fostering an alliance of Young Achievers dedicated to climate causes. A pivotal aspect involves developing an OpenPass4Climate that is portable throughout one's life, designed to empower individuals from ages 10 to 80 to actively engage in climate-related endeavors and take pride in the badges they earn.

Anticipated outcomes include the establishment and growth of a community of climate achievers comprising staff, professors, researchers, and students. This community, acknowledged through the OpenPass4Climate platform without borders, is expected to expand beyond university boundaries to fulfill the aspirations of students seeking Open Badges for their ongoing contributions and to facilitate the acquisition of new knowledge while actively engaging in positive actions.

To effectively identify and evaluate diverse climate commitments, it is imperative to collect information concerning the nature of students' engagement with climate-related activities. This process encompasses both implicit and explicit forms of recognition. Completing this task requires a thorough understanding of current practices in open recognition systems and how they might be applied specifically to climate education.

The rise of open recognition systems

The landscape of educational credentialing is undergoing significant transformation. While conventional academic credentials retain their significance, the educational landscape now embraces more nuanced and adaptable recognition mechanisms. These emerging approaches provide enhanced capacity to document and validate the multifaceted competencies developed across structured educational programs, community-based learning contexts, and self-directed knowledge acquisition pathways. Open badges and micro-credentials have emerged as prominent tools in this evolution, offering verification mechanisms for skills and knowledge that might otherwise go unrecognized (West & Cheng, 2023).

Open recognition systems refer to flexible, technology-enabled frameworks—such as open badges and micro-credentials—that validate learning across formal, non-formal, and informal contexts. These systems enable learners to receive recognition for discrete skills and achievements, regardless of where or how the learning occurred.

While the terms “open badges” and “digital badges” are often used interchangeably, it is important to note their distinctions. “Open badges” specifically refer to a standardized format for digital credentials, such as those adhering to the Mozilla Open Badges standard, which ensures interoperability and portability across platforms. “Digital badges,” on the other hand, is a broader term encompassing any digital representation of skills or achievements, which may or may not follow a specific standard. In the context of climate education, both open badges and broader digital badges offer promising solutions for recognizing interdisciplinary competencies and action-oriented achievements.

The concept of open recognition for learning achievements has gained significant traction. This development is particularly evident as educational pathways become more diverse. Additionally, the workforce increasingly demands more specific and demonstrable competencies. This trend has accelerated since the COVID-19 pandemic, which highlighted the need for flexible, accessible learning options and rapidly verifiable skills (Tamoliune *et al.*, 2023). For climate education specifically, these systems offer the potential to recognize the multidisciplinary knowledge and action-oriented competencies that are essential for addressing complex environmental challenges.

The relevance to climate education

Climate change education presents unique challenges that make it particularly suited to open recognition approaches. First, climate literacy spans multiple disciplines, from natural sciences to social studies, policy, economics, and beyond. Traditional educational structures often struggle to integrate this interdisciplinary knowledge effectively. Second, addressing climate change requires not just knowledge but action and civic engagement, which are rarely recognized in conventional academic credentials. Third, climate education happens across multiple contexts—formal classrooms, community initiatives, workplace projects, and personal advocacy—creating a need for recognition systems that can bridge these varied learning environments.

Open badges and micro-credentials offer promising solutions to these challenges. They can verify discrete competencies across disciplinary boundaries, recognize action-oriented achievements beyond knowledge acquisition, and validate learning regardless of where it occurs (Cumberland *et al.*, 2023). This alignment between the needs of climate education and the affordances of open recognition systems suggests significant potential for their application in this domain.

Purpose and scope of this review

This literature review aims to investigate current practices in open recognition systems, with a particular focus on their application and potential in climate education. It is conducted as part of Work Package 3 (WP3) of the OpenPass4Climate Erasmus+ project, which seeks to identify and evaluate different climate commitments and assess students' perceptions of their needs through an open recognition framework.

Specifically, this review addresses the following objectives:

- To examine the main contributions in the field of open recognition learning, particularly focusing on badges, micro-credentials, and their potential application in climate education contexts;
- To identify key challenges in implementing open recognition systems for climate-related competencies and actions; and
- To synthesize recommendations from existing research for effective implementation of open badges and micro-credentials in climate education.

By addressing these objectives, this review aims to provide a comprehensive foundation for the development of the OpenPass4Climate system, informing both the conceptual framework and practical implementation of open badges for recognizing climate action and learning.

Method

Research design

This review aims to identify, select, and analyze the existing literature on open recognition systems with a focus on their application to climate education. The methodology was designed to gather comprehensive evidence from diverse sources while remaining practical and focused on the specific needs of the OpenPass4Climate project.

Search strategy and sources

Databases

To ensure comprehensive coverage of the literature, the following databases were searched:

- Web of Science
- EBSCOhost
- ERIC (Education Resources Information Center)
- Scopus
- Google Scholar
- Wiley
- PubMed/Europe PMC
- SemanticScholar

The selection of databases was deliberate and methodologically sound. Google Scholar was included for its comprehensive

coverage across disciplines and ability to index a wide range of publication types, including those not captured by traditional academic databases. ERIC (Education Resources Information Center) was selected for its specialized focus on education literature, making it particularly valuable for identifying research on educational badges and credentials. Web of Science and Scopus were chosen for their rigorous indexing standards and citation tracking capabilities, facilitating the identification of highly cited, influential works in the field. The inclusion of EBSCOhost, Wiley, PubMed/Europe PMC, and SemanticScholar further ensured breadth of coverage across different publishers and disciplinary perspectives, which is particularly important given the interdisciplinary nature of climate education and open recognition systems

Additionally, we conducted searches in French, Portuguese, Italian, and German language sources to capture relevant literature from multiple linguistic contexts.

Search terms and query development

The search strategy was developed through an iterative process, focusing on the intersection of open recognition systems and climate or environmental education. The primary search strings used included:

("open education recognition system" OR "open badges" OR "digital badges" OR "micro-credentials") AND ("climate change" OR "environmental actions" OR "ecopedagogical activities")

Additional search strings were developed to refine results by educational context:

("open education recognition system" OR "open badges" OR "digital badges") AND ("climate change" OR "environmental actions" OR "ecopedagogical activities") AND ("K-12" OR "higher education" OR "lifelong learning" OR "general public")

Further search strings focused on methodological aspects, best practices, and international perspectives:

("open education recognition system" OR "open badges" OR "digital badges") AND ("climate change" OR "environmental actions" OR "ecopedagogical activities") AND (methodology OR approach OR implementation)

("open education recognition system" OR "open badges" OR "digital badges") AND ("climate change" OR "environmental actions" OR "ecopedagogical activities") AND ("best practices" OR "successful cases" OR "exemplary models")

("open education recognition system" OR "open badges" OR "digital badges") AND ("climate change" OR "environmental actions" OR "ecopedagogical activities") AND ("international perspective" OR "global initiatives" OR "cross-cultural")

These search strings were adapted as needed for each database and translated for non-English language searches. All search strings and results were documented to ensure transparency.

Search results

Initial database searches yielded a significant number of records across all databases. After applying filters for publication date (2010–2024), peer-reviewed status, and removing duplicates, 477 unique records were identified for initial screening.

Selection criteria and process

Inclusion criteria

Studies were included if they met the following criteria:

- Published between January 1, 2010, and November 30, 2024
- Published in peer-reviewed journals
- Available in full-text format (with university library membership)
- Focus on digital badges, open badges, or micro-credentials in educational or professional development contexts
- Keywords mentioned in the title or abstract

Exclusion criteria

Studies were excluded if they:

- Referred to digital badges when they were not considered as micro-credentials
- Lacked substantive discussion of open recognition systems or their application

Screening and selection process

The selection process consisted of an initial screening of titles and abstracts against the inclusion and exclusion criteria, followed by a full-text review of the remaining articles. This process resulted in a final sample of 69 articles, review papers, book chapters, and reports for analysis.

Data analysis

The analysis focused on identifying key themes, challenges, and recommendations related to open recognition systems for climate education.

Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged:

- The review covers the literature published until January 31, 2025.
- Despite our multilingual approach, language barriers may have affected the comprehensiveness of non-English literature coverage.
- The keyword search requirements may have excluded relevant articles that addressed related concepts but used different terminology.

These limitations notwithstanding, this review provides a solid foundation for understanding the current state of research on open recognition systems for climate education within the context of the OpenPass4Climate project.

Current practices in open recognition systems

The field of open learning recognition has seen significant contributions across various focus areas, each addressing different aspects of educational enhancement and validation of competencies. Across the studies reviewed, the main areas of open recognition learning can be grouped into key focus areas such as:

Badges and micro-credentials

Digital badges and micro-credentials are increasingly vital for recognizing and validating skills across formal and informal learning contexts, particularly in climate education.

It is important to clearly distinguish between micro-credentials and open badges, as these terms are sometimes used interchangeably but represent distinct concepts. Micro-credentials are broader certification units that validate specific skills, knowledge, or competencies, typically requiring assessment and often carrying academic credit value. They represent smaller learning achievements than full degrees and may be stackable toward larger qualifications. Open badges, in contrast, are a specific technological implementation—a digital representation of skills, achievements, or qualities that contains verifiable metadata about the earner, issuer, criteria, and evidence. While all open badges could be considered micro-credentials, not all micro-credentials are implemented as open badges. The key distinction lies in their scope and technical implementation: micro-credentials focus on the certification framework and academic recognition, while open badges emphasize the digital, portable, and verifiable representation of achievements across platforms.

[Oliver \(2019\)](#) defines micro-credentials as certifications of assessed learning that complement or extend formal qualifications. [West and Cheng \(2023\)](#) emphasize their role in open education infrastructure, highlighting affordances such as granular recognition of accomplishments, mastery demonstration, and lifelong portfolio creation, which are especially relevant for documenting climate-related competencies. Similarly, [Wolz et al. \(2021\)](#) underscore their potential to digitize traditional graduation certificates, aligning with employers' digital recruitment processes and enhancing trust through secure, verifiable formats—attributes that could certify climate education achievements effectively.

A systematic review by [Cumberland et al. \(2023\)](#) found a growing interest in micro-credentials, particularly in higher education and workplace settings, where they can function either as pedagogical tools or as credentials that validate competencies. Digital badges represent a specific form of micro-credentialing that is gaining attention among employers and educational institutions alike.

Micro-credentials are seen as a means of certifying smaller attainments of learning than that of a full degree. This insight includes stackable credit, general recognition of prior learning, evidence of graduate attributes, and standards-based

competencies associated with professional practice, promoting a structured approach to skills validation that bridges the gap between academic learning and professional demands (Harris & Wihak, 2018). Authors assessing implementation and perceptions, such as Jirgensons and Kapenieks (2018) and Korhonen *et al.* (2020), found open badges useful for demonstrating competencies in job applications. However, Perkins and Pryor (2021) examined employer awareness and acceptance of digital badges, finding a significant gap in understanding that needs to be addressed for broader adoption. Dyjur and Lindstrom (2017) examined perceptions of digital badges, finding both positive and negative views. Davis and Singh (2015) identified badges as an opportunity to establish learner credibility outside of the original context but noted credibility as a dominant challenge requiring recognition by external audiences.

Micro-credentials demonstrate significant utility in domains outside traditional educational settings. Research conducted by Selvaratnam and Sankey (2021) identifies these compact certifications as offering Australian higher education institutions viable strategic directions for long-term sustainability, with particular effectiveness demonstrated in abbreviated learning modules and advanced graduate-level educational offerings. Similarly, a review by Varadarajan *et al.* (2023) suggests that micro-credentials can function as learning pathways, employment pathways, and qualification frameworks, serving the needs of different stakeholders including learners, educational institutions, employers, and governmental bodies.

According to Mah (2016), integrating micro-credentials into institutional programs can enhance their value and utility, making them more accessible and impactful for all stakeholders. Pollard and Vincent (2022) also proposed to align principles of micro-credentials with university missions and embed them into the curriculum. However, in this higher education context, Trepulé *et al.* (2021) emphasized the importance of clear evaluation and recognition criteria for digital badges to increase their value for assessment and recognition. In this line, the framework for the design and development of open badge systems proposed by Devedžić and Jovanović (2015) can be particularly helpful.

A recent perspective piece highlights how digital badges can offer self-guided learning options that allow individuals to develop both professionally and personally at their own pace. Currie *et al.* (2023) highlight how digital credentialing systems function as intrinsic motivation catalysts, stimulating investment in ongoing professional growth. These systems additionally create beneficial competitive dynamics that enhance learning outcomes, particularly when participation remains voluntary—a condition that promotes increased innovative thinking, deeper interaction with educational content, and heightened learner fulfillment.

Empirical research demonstrates the substantial motivational influence of open badge systems within recognition-based learning environments (Abramovich *et al.*, 2013). Investigations by Cheng *et al.* (2018) reveal how digital credentialing

mechanisms strengthen learners' self-regulation capabilities by supporting structured objective formulation, enhancing commitment to established targets, managing assignment difficulty levels, and integrating evaluative input. Research further suggests that shifting from traditional grading approaches to open badge frameworks redirects learner attention toward comprehensive skill acquisition and knowledge development (Tomić *et al.*, 2024). Carey and Stefaniak (2018) found that skill-based badges are more valuable than participation badges.

In climate education, open badges provide a promising avenue for acknowledging interdisciplinary skills essential for environmental action. For instance, Rollin (2021) demonstrates their use in higher education to assess transversal skills like critical thinking and collaboration—key competencies for addressing climate challenges. This aligns with the findings by West and Cheng (2023) on how micro-credentials can support personalized learning pathways, motivating learners to develop sustainability skills through self-directed efforts.

Research by Miller and Jorre de St Jorre (2024) on employer perspectives in environmental science further validates the potential of micro-credentials in climate education. Through interviews with environmental professionals, they found that employers value alternative sources of evidence when recruiting graduates and showed enthusiasm for micro-credentials that could demonstrate specific environmental competencies, though they emphasized the need for rigorous standards and clear contextual information about these credentials.

Recent applications in Nordic coastal tourism education further demonstrate the practical value of micro-credentials and open badges in sustainability contexts. Halttunen *et al.* (2024) highlight how these credentials provide flexible, cost-effective pathways for tourism workers to develop sustainability competencies despite geographical constraints in remote destinations. Their research found that both tourism companies and destination management organizations recognized the complementary value of industry certificates and open badges for verifying skills in sustainability practices—with certificates meeting operational standards and badges demonstrating advanced expertise development. This application suggests that open badges could bridge formal education with practical environmental outcomes, enhancing learner engagement across diverse contexts, including the climate education field.

Additionally, Cox *et al.* (2020), cited in the ALN Climate Adaptation Micro-credential Strategy (Cox, 2021), developed an openly licensed Climate Adaptation Competency Framework that aligns with micro-credential programs targeting professionals who need climate adaptation capabilities. Their framework identifies five competency domains with five sub-competencies each, structured to support criterion-based professional development in climate adaptation. This approach demonstrates how micro-credentials can be strategically designed to address workforce gaps in climate knowledge and skills, particularly in areas requiring strategic foresight for adaptation challenges.

Open Educational Resources (OER) and Practices (OEP), MOOCs, and online learning

The adoption of open educational resources (OER) and open educational practices (OEP) has been widely explored, offering substantial benefits for enhancing learning accessibility and quality, particularly in climate education. [West and Cheng \(2023\)](#) argue that OER, when paired with open micro-credentials, forms a comprehensive open education infrastructure that supports personalized learning pathways—an approach that could democratize access to climate literacy.

[Littlejohn and Hood \(2017\)](#) demonstrated that OER engagement promotes three levels of learning for educators, which can be leveraged to structure workplace learning opportunities. [van de Laar et al. \(2024\)](#) found that open-access online courses were valued by Ph.D. students, although open micro-credentials did not incentivize course completion for this population. [Bozkurt et al. \(2019\)](#) and [Knox \(2013\)](#) highlighted the growing importance of openness in education, while also noticing challenges such as the divide between the global north and south in research output and the need for a critical exploration of the relationships between technology and education. [Jung and Lee \(2020\)](#) examined cultural factors influencing OER adoption and found that habit is a strong determinant across cultures, although other factors such as performance expectations and social influence also play a critical role. [Bossu and Fountain \(2015\)](#) introduced an open micro-course to build capacity in OEP. [Adedoyin and Altinay \(2023\)](#) examined factors that influence students' intentions to use OER. [Knox \(2013\)](#) proposed the inclusion of “open processes” in OEP. [Ramirez-Montoya \(2020\)](#) discussed how open education can support educational processes. Open science and scholarship promote transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in research. [Corrall and Pinfield \(2014\)](#) discussed the theoretical underpinnings of openness in different domains, emphasizing the importance of an integrated approach to open practices. [Littlejohn and Hood \(2017\)](#) studied how educators learn through engagement with OER, demonstrating the transformative potential of open educational resources in professional development. [Askeroth and Newby \(2020\)](#) noted that badges are well-suited for adult learners in less formal educational settings.

Massive open online courses (MOOCs) have been instrumental in providing scalable and flexible learning opportunities. The most significant contribution came from [Ramirez-Montoya et al. \(2022\)](#), who identified key factors influencing MOOC effectiveness, such as perceived usefulness, self-efficacy, and achievement motivation, which are critical to designing effective online learning experiences. [Gates and Walters \(2015\)](#) explored the relevance of MOOCs in social work education, highlighting their potential in delivering professional training. [Kopp and Ebner \(2017\)](#) found that the awarding of certificates has an impact on MOOC learners, but the impact varies depending on the target group, commitment, and usability. Other studies have contributed by examining approaches to assessment, such as [Farrow et al. \(2021\)](#), who proposed identity verification strategies for MOOC platforms, and [Chauhan \(2014\)](#), who discussed automated assessment techniques in MOOCs.

“Smart systems” are being developed to track and predict learner behavior. [Bossu and Fountain \(2015\)](#) acknowledge that Applaud—a specific online scheme system to gain recognition—has had a positive impact on learning and teaching at the Open University, supporting professional development, career development, and reflective practice. [Charleer et al. \(2013\)](#) found that gamified dashboards such as Navi Badgeboard helped with awareness of personal activities, while Navi Surface improved collaboration and reflection.

Further applications of OER and MOOCs in climate education underscore their synergy with open recognition systems. [Cieply and Grand \(2019\)](#) analyzed the use of open badges in higher education to recognize competencies developed through OER-based learning, offering a scalable model for climate education that fosters critical engagement with ecological issues. This complements the emphasis of [West and Cheng \(2023\)](#) on micro-credentials supporting inquiry-based learning, which could enhance climate-focused curricula across educational levels.

Recognition of prior and non-formal learning

Regarding the recognition of prior and non-formal learning, [Schmidt et al. \(2009\)](#) proposed a peer-based method of assessment and recognition that uses online communities to provide a credible alternative to traditional assessment methods. [Tereseviciene et al. \(2020\)](#) studied the recognition of open online learning in higher education and identified challenges in adapting to changes in the labor market. [Friesen and Wihak \(2013\)](#) explored the links between open educational contexts and prior learning assessment and recognition (PLAR). [Harris and Wihak \(2018\)](#) identified synergies in the recognition of non-formal learning. The integration of technology in higher education is essential to adapt to the changing demands of the workforce. Therefore, [Lang \(2023\)](#) argued that universities should adopt digital micro-credentials to meet the changing needs of the workforce and facilitate a shift toward more flexible and relevant educational offerings. [Orr et al. \(2019\)](#) identified archetypes of technology-enabled higher education, providing a framework for understanding different levels of digital adoption in institutions. [Volungevičienė et al. \(2020\)](#) supported the shift to learner-centered, multidimensional teaching models that leverage new digital devices to create more engaging and effective learning environments. [Zawacki-Richter et al. \(2020\)](#) provided a comprehensive review of open and distance learning research, identifying trends and gaps in the current landscape.

The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of distance education across all types of schools, creating both opportunities and challenges for Open Universities ([Lyu, 2023](#)). While this expansion has made micro-credentials more relevant, it also raises concerns about how to effectively implement online teaching and maintain educational quality. The pandemic has stimulated the need for developing new competencies and personalized, competency-based, flexible, and collaborative professional development ([Varadarajan et al., 2023](#)). These changes have highlighted the importance of micro-credentials as tools for rapid upskilling in an educational landscape that increasingly embraces online delivery modalities.

Another contribution of reviewed research on open learning is the recognition of competency frameworks and sustainability in education, which are critical to aligning skills with evolving industry needs and promoting lifelong learning. [Fitsilis \(2024\)](#) emphasized the importance of competency frameworks in Education 4.0 that align individual skills with organizational goals. [Annelin and Boström \(2022\)](#) analyzed questionnaire assessment tools for measuring sustainability competencies and identified the need for comprehensive assessment tools that span multiple disciplines.

Challenges

Standardization and definitional issues

The lack of standardized definitions and criteria for openness leads to inconsistent results. Different interpretations of what constitutes open learning recognition can lead to differences in implementation and effectiveness, as noted in several studies.

A persistent challenge in the micro-credential landscape is the absence of global standardization, complicating their application in climate education. For instance, a climate adaptation course might be valued differently across regions due to varying credit definitions, hindering learners' ability to transfer credentials internationally. [Ahsan *et al.* \(2023\)](#) note the lack of consensus on micro-credential definitions and credit values across universities, industries, and governments, a concern echoed by [Wolz *et al.* \(2021\)](#), who identify terminological ambiguity in higher education institutions as a barrier to adoption. For example, the European Credit Transfer System defines micro-credentials as conferring a minimum of 5 ECTS credits, while the New Zealand Qualifications Authority bounds them between 5 and 40 credits ([Varadarajan *et al.*, 2023](#)).

Institutional coherence and coordination

One of the challenges reported in the reviewed studies was the lack of coherence and coordination between different open initiatives. It has been highlighted this issue of the unified policy approach to integrate different open domains to maximize their potential benefits for learners ([Corrall & Pinfield, 2014](#)). It has also been mentioned as a limitation in the widespread adoption and implementation of open learning recognition tools that it requires significant cultural change within educational institutions.

Stakeholder awareness and acceptance

[Perkins and Pryor \(2021\)](#) found a significant gap in employer awareness and acceptance of digital badges, indicating the need for broader educational efforts to increase understanding and acceptance in formal and informal learning environments. [Miller and Jorre de St Jorre \(2024\)](#) further confirmed this challenge in environmental science contexts, where employers expressed support for micro-credentials but required more context about their application and assurance of their rigor.

The research by [Halttunen *et al.* \(2024\)](#) additionally revealed unique challenges in implementing open badges for sustainability education in tourism, particularly in remote or seasonal

destinations where access to training is limited by geographical and economic constraints. Their findings suggest that while digital credentials can overcome some of these barriers, they must be designed with awareness of contextual limitations like connectivity issues or variable workforce composition throughout the year.

[Cumberland *et al.* \(2023\)](#) conducted a systematic review of the digital badge landscape in educational and workplace settings, identifying two main uses: as pedagogical tools and as micro-credentials. Their work identifies persistent confusion in nomenclature and a divergence in findings that suggests the need for further exploration. The authors note that for digital badges to be valuable, employers must recognize them as such, which presents both a challenge and an opportunity for collaboration between educational institutions and the labor market.

Technological and implementation barriers

In addition, technological challenges such as scalability, privacy, and storage capacity, particularly with blockchain technology, pose significant barriers. [Jirgensons and Kapenieks \(2018\)](#) discuss these issues in the context of implementing blockchain for digital learning. [Korhonen *et al.* \(2019\)](#) reported that learners attached earned open badges to their ePortfolios and shared them in digital environments to showcase their skills. Organizational barriers, including resistance from traditional academic and publishing sectors, also hinder the adoption of open practices. In addition to technological challenges, sharing research data and educational resources often requires additional effort, which can be a restraint for educators and researchers. The additional workload and lack of support mechanisms are significant barriers to wider adoption.

Research by [Ahsan *et al.* \(2023\)](#) also identified technological readiness as a critical factor in micro-credential implementation. Without supportive learning technology, implementing micro-credentials in higher education becomes impractical. The authors noted that blockchain technology could potentially enhance the authenticity of micro-credentials through certified digital documents, though further research on its adoption is needed. [Wolz *et al.* \(2021\)](#) discuss blockchain's potential to enhance credential security, yet note scalability and privacy challenges that could hinder its use in certifying environmental achievements. A French report by [Rollin \(2022\)](#) identifies methodological issues—reliability, validity, and equity—in assessing transversal skills via open badges, underscoring the need for robust frameworks to ensure equitable recognition of climate education outcomes across diverse learners.

Climate education specific challenges

The Climate Adaptation Micro-credential Strategy ([Cox, 2021](#)) also points to the challenge of creating comprehensive recognition systems that can effectively connect disparate educational offerings related to climate adaptation. The strategy highlights the need for constant interaction between didactics and professional practice to ensure that micro-credentials meet real-world needs in addressing climate challenges. This

connects to broader concerns about fragmentation in sustainability education, where many initiatives exist but often lack coherent frameworks that allow for progressive skill-building across different contexts.

Recommendations

The literature review highlights several key recommendations for the effective implementation of micro-credentials and digital badges. These include integrating them into institutional programs to ensure they add value and are easy to use with clear metrics; embedding them in the curriculum using critical and reflective pedagogy (Mah, 2016; Pollard & Vincent, 2022); and making digital credentials easy to understand and valuable to employers and also aligning pedagogical practices with employer needs (Perkins & Pryor, 2021). McNamara and Sun (2021) called for a global agreement on standards for the recognition, creation, validation, and distribution of micro-credentials and digital badges.

Institutional integration and policy

The systematic analysis of digital credentialing practices by Cumberland *et al.* (2023) recommends that tertiary education organizations develop governance frameworks and institutional regulations prior to implementation. Their findings emphasize the necessity of creating structured classification systems that delineate how micro-credentials integrate within institution-specific educational frameworks. Their research identifies concentrated learning experiences and advanced degree programming as optimal starting points for micro-credential integration due to their reduced implementation risks. The authors highlight the importance of standardization to ensure portability between institutions, an aspect that has also been pointed out by other recent research, including McNamara and Sun (2021).

Employer and stakeholder alignment

Recent reviews indicate that employers value micro-credentials as a way to fulfill their specific requirements and acknowledge skills using digital badges (Varadarajan *et al.*, 2023). However, employers express concerns about the consistency of micro-credentials, their integrity, and the potential for fraudulent credentials. As noted by Kahle-Piasecki *et al.* (2024), the success of micro-credentials in the industry depends on standardization and recognition, suggesting the need for partnerships between higher education institutions, industry, and government agencies. This aligns with Perkins and Pryor (2021), who stress making credentials valuable and understandable to employers.

Technical and design aspects

Badge system design. Develop badge systems that provide visible recognition with metadata linked to validating evidence of educational achievement (Gibson *et al.*, 2023; Gibson *et al.*, 2015). Design badge systems that encourage teamwork and public display of achievement (Goodyear & Nathan-Roberts, 2017).

Technical ecosystem. Sousa-Vieira *et al.* (2021) suggest that the successful implementation of digital badges in higher

education requires a comprehensive technical ecosystem. This includes considerations for storage, security, and administrative management of badges to maintain their integrity and authenticity. According to their conceptual framework, the badge module should include properties such as name, description, icon, text, visibility settings, and type (automatic, manual, or by contest).

Blockchain solutions. Wolz *et al.* (2021) propose blockchain-based systems to secure digital credentials, offering a scalable solution for documenting lifelong climate learning—a strategy that could build trust among EU stakeholders.

Pedagogical approaches

Werth and Williams (2022) advocate building on open pedagogy to democratize learning experiences. McDaniel (2016) suggested the use of a design matrix and design recommendations for badges derived from diverse perspectives. Addressing cultural and contextual differences is essential to effectively adopt open learning recognition tools. Additionally, Mah (2016) and Pollard and Vincent (2022) emphasize embedding micro-credentials in the curriculum using critical and reflective pedagogy to enhance educational value.

Applications in climate education

Environmental science context. Based on their research in environmental science fields, Miller and Jorre de St Jorre (2024) recommend that micro-credential developers provide clear context about how these credentials can be used in professional settings and ensure rigorous assessment standards to build employer confidence. Their findings suggest that environmental employers value multiple lines of evidence when recruiting, and micro-credentials could serve as valuable supplementary validation of skills if properly contextualized.

Nordic tourism education. In the context of Nordic tourism education, Halttunen *et al.* (2024) suggest a blended learning approach that combines on-site workplace training with digital badges and MOOCs to accommodate learning in remote destinations. Their research emphasizes the importance of establishing common proficiency goals as frames of reference for sustainability competencies and providing flexible recognition mechanisms that can validate both existing and newly developed skills. This approach could be particularly relevant for climate education in contexts where geographical barriers limit access to traditional educational opportunities.

Climate adaptation strategy. The Climate Adaptation Micro-credential Strategy (Cox, 2021) proposes a strategic approach for climate education that involves basing micro-credentials on open competency frameworks that clearly articulate required skills across different domains of climate adaptation work. Their recommendations include:

- Certifying courses using established competency frameworks to provide clear standards for employers and learners
- Designing micro-credentials for hybrid delivery with both synchronous and asynchronous components to accommodate working professionals

- Awarding credentials digitally with verifiable critical information summaries that provide metadata about the competencies achieved
- Creating pathways for prior learning assessment that allow experienced professionals to demonstrate existing climate adaptation skills

These recommendations are particularly relevant for developing open recognition systems in climate education as they address both pedagogical design and practical implementation concerns.

Accessibility and learner agency. To advance open recognition in climate education, both accessibility and learner agency should be prioritized. [Jean-Marie and Millet \(2022\)](#) advocate making badge tools accessible to all educational actors, ensuring equitable participation in climate-focused programs.

Future research directions

Further research and development are essential to advance the recognition of open learning. For instance, [Jirgensons and Kapenieks \(2018\)](#) suggest conducting case studies to explore the potential of blockchain technology in different courses and programs. [Jung and Lee \(2020\)](#) suggested conducting qualitative or mixed methods studies to understand educators' use of OER within and across cultures. [Lee \(2020\)](#) recommended focusing efforts on opening higher education to disadvantaged groups and collecting real-life stories to inform practice. [Randall et al. \(2019\)](#) recommended further research to support the use of instructional design assistants for badge creation, as innovative pedagogical approaches and thoughtful design are key to successful implementation. The scholarly discourse surrounding recognition systems continues to evolve, with [Roy and Clark \(2019\)](#) particularly emphasizing the necessity for expanded investigation across varied educational and cultural environments. Contemporary research affirms the enduring relevance of digital credentialing mechanisms within educational innovation ([Farmer & West, 2016](#)), yet significant knowledge gaps persist that require targeted investigation to advance understanding of their full potential and limitations.

Conclusion

Research on the recognition of open learning, including digital badges, micro-credentials, and OER underscores their potential to transform education and professional development, particularly in climate-related fields. However, realizing this potential requires overcoming significant challenges related to standardization, credibility, technological barriers, and integration with existing systems.

The literature highlights the need for stronger partnerships between higher education and employers to establish effective digital credentialing systems. The recommendations provided by researchers offer a roadmap for integrating these tools into education systems, ensuring quality and relevance, and fostering a culture of openness and inclusiveness. Continued research and collaboration among stakeholders are essential to advance the field and fully realize the benefits of open learning credentials.

This review demonstrates the multifaceted nature of research on open credentialing, including aspects of design, psychology, credibility, educational outcomes, specific applications, engagement factors, and stakeholder perceptions. Key contributions include: (1) documenting the rise of micro-credentials and open badges in validating climate competencies, (2) identifying standardization and employer awareness as critical challenges, and (3) synthesizing actionable recommendations for climate education integration. Future research should focus on developing best practices for badge design, exploring their long-term impact on learning outcomes, and investigating ways to increase their recognition and value in the labor market, particularly in climate education contexts.

The emerging applications in Nordic regions and climate adaptation learning networks suggest promising directions for open recognition systems in climate education. These approaches emphasize the importance of contextualized, competency-based frameworks that can accommodate both formal and informal learning pathways while addressing the practical challenges of climate adaptation work.

Recent systematic reviews emphasize the need for an integrative approach to micro-credential implementation that considers the perspectives of all stakeholders—learners, higher education institutions, employers, and governmental bodies. The success of micro-credentialing systems will depend on addressing challenges related to standardization, technological readiness, and stakeholder perceptions while maximizing opportunities for flexible, personalized learning pathways and enhanced employability in climate-related fields.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability statement

No data are associated with this article.

References

Abramovich S, Schunn C, Higashi RM: **Are badges useful in education?: it depends upon the type of badge and expertise of learner.** *Educ Technol Res Dev.* 2013; **61**(2): 217–232.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Adedoyin OB, Altinay F: **Open educational resources: evaluation of students' intention to use and motivation to create.** *Br J Educ Technol.* 2023; **54**(6): 1790–1813.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

- Ahsan K, Akbar S, Kam B, *et al.*: **Implementation of micro-credentials in higher education: a systematic literature review.** *Educ Inf Technol.* 2023; **28**(10): 13505–13540.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Annelin A, Boström GO: **An assessment of key sustainability competencies: a review of scales and propositions for validation.** *Int J Sustain High Educ.* 2022; **24**(9): 53–69.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Askeroth JH, Newby TJ: **Digital badge use in specific learner groups.** *International Journal of Innovative Teaching and Learning in Higher Education.* 2020; **1**(1): 1–15.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bossu C, Fountain W: **Capacity-building in open education: an Australian approach.** *Open Praxis.* 2015; **7**(2): 123–132.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bozkurt A, Koseoglu S, Singh L: **An analysis of peer reviewed publications on openness in education in half a century: trends and patterns in the open hemisphere.** *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology.* 2019; **35**(4).
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Carey KL, Stefaniak JE: **An exploration of the utility of digital badging in higher education settings.** *Educ Technol Res Dev.* 2018; **66**(5): 1211–1229.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Charleer S, Klerkx J, Santos JL, *et al.*: **Improving awareness and reflection through collaborative, interactive visualizations of badges.** Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Awareness and Reflection in Technology-Enhanced Learning (ARTEL13), Edited by Milos Kravcic, Birgit Krogstie, Adam Moore, Viktoria Pammer, Lucia Pannese, Michael Prilla, Wolfgang Reinhardt, and Thomas Daniel Ullmann. CEUR Workshop Proceedings, ISSN 1613-0073, Paphos, Cyprus, 2013; **1103**: 69–81.
[Reference Source](#)
- Chauhan A: **Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs): emerging trends in assessment and accreditation.** *Digital Education Review.* 2014; **25**(1): 7–17.
[Reference Source](#)
- Cheng Z, Watson SL, Newby TJ: **Goal setting and open digital badges in higher education.** *Techtrends.* 2018; **62**(2): 190–196.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Cieply S, Grand I: **Quels usages pour les open badges dans l'enseignement supérieur? Analyse de la diffusion d'une innovation à l'IAE caen.** *Management & Avenir.* 2019; **113**(7): 15–38.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Corrall S, Pinfield S: **Coherence of "open" initiatives in higher education and research: framing a policy agenda.** *(i)Conference 2014 - Breaking Down Walls - Culture • Context • Computing; held at Berlin School of Library and Information Science, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Mar. 4–7.* Berlin, (iSchools Inc.), 2014.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Cox R: **Climate adaptation micro-credential strategy.** Adaptation Learning Network, Royal Roads University, 2021.
[Reference Source](#)
- Cox R, Niederer S, Forsmann V, *et al.*: **Climate adaptation competency framework.** Adaptation Learning Network, Royal Roads University, 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
- Cumberland DM, Deckard TG, Kahle-Piasecki L, *et al.*: **Making sense of the digital badging landscape in education and workplace settings: a scoping review of the empirical literature.** *European Journal of Training and Development.* 2023; **48**(1/2): 253–275.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Currie S, Eby L, Feller A, *et al.*: **Moving with the times: the use of digital badges as a learning option.** *Development and Learning in Organizations: An International Journal.* 2023; **37**(3): 35–36.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Davis K, Singh S: **Digital badges in afterschool learning: documenting the perspectives and experiences of students and educators.** *Comput Educ.* 2015; **88**: 72–83.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Devedžić V, Jovanović J: **Developing open badges: a comprehensive approach.** *Educ Technol Res Dev.* 2015; **63**(4): 603–620.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Dyjur P, Lindstrom G: **Perceptions and uses of digital badges for professional learning development in higher education.** *Techtrends.* 2017; **61**(4): 386–392.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Farmer T, West RE: **Opportunities and challenges with digital open badges.** *Educ Technol.* 2016; **56**(5): 45–48.
[Reference Source](#)
- Farrow R, Ferguson R, Weller M, *et al.*: **Assessment and recognition of MOOCs: the state of the art.** *Journal of Innovation in Polytechnic Education.* 2021; **3**(1): 15–26.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fitsilis P: **Navigating the skills revolution: the essential role of competence frameworks.** *Qeios.* 2024; 1–17.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Friesen N, Wihak C: **From OER to PLAR: credentialing for open education.** *Open Praxis.* 2013; **5**(1): 49–58.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gates T, Walters A: **Are MOOCs the next trend in social work?: implications for practice education.** *Adv Soc Work.* 2015; **16**(1): 184–201.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gibson D, Kovanovic V, Ifenthaler D, *et al.*: **Learning theories for Artificial Intelligence promoting learning processes.** *Brit J Educ Technol.* 2023; **54**(5): 1125–1146.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gibson D, Ostashevski N, Flintoff K, *et al.*: **Digital badges in education.** *Educ Inf Technol.* 2015; **20**(2): 403–410.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Goodyear M, Nathan-Roberts D: **Gamification and the design of badges in relation to educational achievement.** *Proc Hum Factors Ergon Soc Annu Meet.* 2017; **61**(1): 1229–1233.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Halttunen T, Brauer S, Jutila S: **Role of micro-credentials and open badges in sustainable tourism education.** In: C. Dragin-Jensen, G. Kwiatkowski, & O. Oklevik (Eds.), *Nordic coastal tourism: sustainability, trends, practices, and opportunities.* Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024; 229–246.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Harris J, Wihak C: **The Recognition of Non-Formal Education in higher education: where are we now, and are we learning from experience?** *Int J E-Learn Distance Educ.* 2018; **33**(1).
[Reference Source](#)
- Jean-Marie E, Millet F: **Open badge: Développer l'accessibilité des outils, développer les usages.** *Badgeons les compétences en Normandie 2022.* Caen, France, 2022.
[Reference Source](#)
- Jirgensons M, Kapenieks J: **Blockchain and the future of digital learning credential assessment and management.** *J Teach Educ Sustain.* 2018; **20**(1): 145–156.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Jung I, Lee J: **A cross-cultural approach to the adoption of Open Educational Resources in higher education.** *Brit J Educ Technol.* 2020; **51**(1): 263–280.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kahle-Piasecki L, Bereza M, Cumberland DM: **Digital badges: a pilot study of employer perceptions.** *Small Business Institute Journal.* 2024; **20**(2): 19–27.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Knox J: **The limitations of access alone: moving towards open processes in education technology.** *Open Praxis.* 2013; **5**(1): 21–29.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kopp M, Ebner M: **Certification of MOOCs: advantages, challenges and practical experiences.** *Revista Espanola de Pedagogia.* 2017; **75**(266): 83–100.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Korhonen AM, Lakkala M, Veermans M: **Identifying vocational student teachers' competence using an ePortfolio.** *Eur J Workplace Innov.* 2019; **5**(1): 41.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Korhonen AM, Ruhalahti S, Niinimäki J: **Finnish vocational teachers' competences made visible by open badges.** *J High Educ Theory Pract.* 2020; **20**(6): 141–149.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Lang J: **Workforce upskilling: can universities meet the challenges of lifelong learning?** *The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology.* 2023; **40**(5): 388–400.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Lee K: **Who opens online distance education, to whom, and for what?** *Distance Educ.* 2020; **41**(2): 186–200.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Littlejohn A, Hood N: **How educators build knowledge and expand their practice: the case of open education resources.** *Brit J Educ Technol.* 2017; **48**(2): 499–510.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Lyu D: **Harnessing micro-credentials to innovate teaching in the Open University of China: opportunities and challenges.** *Creat Educ.* 2023; **14**(5): 899–913.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Mah DK: **Learning analytics and digital badges: potential impact on student retention in higher education.** *Tech Know Learn.* 2016; **21**(3): 285–305.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- McDaniel R: **A taxonomy for digital badge design in medical technologies.** *2016 IEEE International Conference on Serious Games and Applications for Health (SeGAH).* (IEEE), Orlando, FL, USA, May 11–13, 2016; 1–8.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- McNamara B, Sun Q: **Micro-credentialing in adult learning: international considerations.** *70th Annual AAACE Conference - Moving the Needle: Digital Divide, Social Justice, and Adult Education.* Commission for International Adult Education (Bowie, MD), Miramar Beach FL, USA, October 5–8, 2021; 121–132.
[Reference Source](#)
- Miller KK, Jorre de St Jorre T: **Digital micro-credentials in environmental science: an employer perspective on valued evidence of skills.** *Teach High Educ.* 2024; **29**(4): 1058–1074.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Oliver B: **Making micro-credentials work for learners, employers and providers.** Deakin University, 2019.
[Reference Source](#)

Orr D, Weller M, Farrow R: **How is digitalisation affecting the flexibility and openness of higher education provision? Results of a global survey using a new conceptual model.** *J Interact Media Educ.* 2019; **2019**(1): 5.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Perkins J, Pryor M: **Digital badges: pinning down employer challenges.** *Journal of Teaching and Learning for Graduate Employability.* 2021; **12**(1): 24–38.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Pollard V, Vincent A: **Micro-credentials: a postdigital counternarrative.** *Postdigit Sci Educ.* 2022; **4**(3): 843–859.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Ramirez-Montoya MS: **Challenges for open education with educational innovation: a systematic literature review.** *Sustainability.* 2020; **12**(17): 7053.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Ramirez-Montoya MS, Martínez-Pérez S, Rodríguez-Abitia G, et al.: **Digital accreditations in MOOC-based training on sustainability: factors that influence terminal efficiency.** *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology.* 2022; **38**(2): 162–180.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Randall DL, Farmer T, West RE: **Effectiveness of undergraduate instructional design assistants in scaling a teacher education open badge system.** *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education.* 2019; **19**(4): 825–849.
[Reference Source](#)

Rollin B: **L'open-badge: un outil au service de l'évaluation et de la reconnaissance de compétences transversales dans l'enseignement supérieur? Evaluer.** *Journal international de recherche en éducation et formation.* 2021; **7**(3): 47–72.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Rollin B: **L'évaluation par open-badges dans l'enseignement supérieur: les enjeux méthodologiques relevés lors d'une expérimentation.** *Congrès international d'Actualité de la Recherche en Éducation et en Formation (AREF).* Lausanne, Switzerland. September 2022, 2022.
[Reference Source](#)

Roy S, Clark D: **Digital badges, do they live up to the hype?** *Br J Educ Technol.* 2019; **50**(5): 2619–2636.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Schmidt JP, Geith C, Håklev S, et al.: **Peer-to-peer recognition of learning in open education.** *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning.* 2009; **10**(5).
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Selvaratnam RM, Sankey M: **An integrative literature review of the implementation of micro-credentials in higher education: implications for practice in Australasia.** *Journal of Teaching and Learning for Graduate Employability.* 2021; **12**(1): 1–17.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Sousa-Vieira ME, Ferrero-Castro D, López-Ardao JC: **Design, development and use of a digital badges system in higher education.** *Appl Sci.* 2021; **12**(1): 220.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Tamoliune G, Greenspon R, Tereseviciene M, et al.: **Exploring the potential of micro-credentials: a systematic literature review.** *Front Educ.* 2023; **7**: 1006811.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Tereseviciene M, Trepule E, Dauksiene E, et al.: **Are universities ready to recognize Open Online Learning?** *Int Educ Stud.* 2020; **13**(2): 21.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Tomić B, Jovanović J, Milikić N, et al.: **Open badges and achievement goal orientation: a study with high-performing student programmers.** *J Comput High Educ.* 2024; **36**(2): 523–545.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Trepulé E, Volungeviciene A, Tereseviciene M, et al.: **How to increase the value of digital badges for assessment and recognition in higher education. A university case.** *Inform Educ.* 2021; **20**(1): 131–152.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

van de Laar M, West RE, Cosma P, et al.: **The value of educational microcredentials in open access online education: a doctoral education case.** *Open Learn J Open Distance e-Learn.* 2024; **39**(4): 373–386.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Varadarajan S, Koh JHL, Daniel BK: **A systematic review of the opportunities and challenges of micro-credentials for multiple stakeholders: learners, employers, higher education institutions and government.** *Int J Educ Technol High Educ.* 2023; **20**(1): 13.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Volungeviciene A, Tereseviciene M, Ehlers UD: **When is open and online learning relevant for curriculum change in higher education? Digital and network society perspective.** *Electron J E-Learn.* 2020; **18**(1): 88–101.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Werth E, Williams K: **The why of open pedagogy: a value-first conceptualization for enhancing instructor praxis.** *Smart Learn Environ.* 2022; **9**(1): 10.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

West RE, Cheng Z: **Digital credential evolution.** In: *Handbook of Open, Distance and Digital Education.* Springer, 2023; 1197–1216.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Wolz E, Gottlieb M, Pongratz H: **Digital credentials in higher education institutions: a literature review.** In: *Innovation Through Information Systems.* Springer, 2021; **48**: 125–140.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Zawacki-Richter O, Conrad D, Bozkurt A, et al.: **Elements of open education: an invitation to future research.** *Int Rev Res Open Distrib Learn.* 2020; **21**(3): 319–334.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 1

Reviewer Report 18 June 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21685.r54673>

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Alexandra Okada

Open University, Milton Keynes, UK

The paper addresses a very interesting and relevant topic. Some key suggestions to enhance its rigor include making the Methodology and Findings sections more concise and providing a clearer reference to support the approach adopted.

About the Abstract

The abstract presents a generally clear and well-structured overview of the paper. However, to enhance its coherence, precision, and overall impact, several areas could be improved with more concise and specific language.

The abstract would benefit from explicitly clarifying the scope and nature of the literature review. Which method was used?

Clarification of Open Educational Resources (OER) Recognition

The mention of OER in the context of recognition is somewhat vague. It is not clear whether (e.g. OER Participation, Completion, Certification?) or other forms of recognition are being referenced. Please specify the exact nature of recognition related to OER that the paper addresses to avoid ambiguity.

Specification of Challenges

The abstract references "challenges" but does so in general terms. More precise identification of which challenges are addressed is important for clarity. For instance, the terms "standardization," "technological integration," and "stakeholder collaboration" are broad and would benefit from further explanation or examples. Citing specific, well-defined challenges will strengthen the paper's positioning and help readers grasp the precise obstacles in the field.

Rationale Behind Findings

The abstract notes a growing importance and need for integration of learning recognition / qualifications (e.g. badges, credentials,) but the rationale or evidence supporting this claim is not sufficiently clear. It would be helpful to briefly indicate why this integration is important, for example by highlighting the impact, gap, or opportunity it addresses for learners and professional

development on Climate Education.

Focus of Conclusion

The conclusion, as described in the abstract, could be more sharply focused. Instead of mentioning promising practices summarise recommendations drawn and new directions or areas for further study.

The abstract is key for providing stronger closure and a clear takeaway message aligned with the paper's aims.

About the paper

The methodology states that the criteria for the literature review: only publications in peer-reviewed journals. However, the final sample consists of a variety of content types: 69 articles, review papers, book chapters, and reports. This must be revised for consistency.

Please clarify your literature review approach—e.g., is it a narrative review, scoping review, or another type? While you mention peer-reviewed sources, your final sample includes diverse materials such as book chapters and reports. If the review is not fully systematic, please explain your selection rationale and method clearly.

Would it be possible to include a table of results indicating journals (for articles), publishers (for book chapters), and funders (for research reports), along with the year and topic/field? Such a table, accompanied by a brief explanation, would be very helpful for readers to familiarize themselves with the literature before engaging with your findings.

Considering the paper's focus on climate education, significant findings related to this area could be made more visible and, if possible, extended to include more details about the learning outcomes and approaches for effective definition through micro-credentials, digital badging, or OER completion. For example:

In this paragraph: "In climate education, open badges offer a promising way to acknowledge interdisciplinary skills essential for environmental action. Rollin (2021) demonstrates their use in higher education to assess transversal skills such as critical thinking and collaboration—key competencies for addressing climate challenges. This aligns with findings by West and Cheng (2023), who show how micro-credentials can support personalized learning pathways, motivating learners to develop sustainability skills through self-directed efforts."

Could you clarify how Rollin (2021) assesses transversal skills like critical thinking and collaboration and criteria used to provide open badges? How do West and Cheng (2023) support personalized learning pathways and their evaluation for recognition? Furthermore, how do Miller and Jorre de St Jorre (2024) exemplify micro-credentials demonstrating specific environmental competencies? Which competencies are emphasized, and what aspects do they highlight regarding standards and the missing contextual information about these credentials?

There is significant information about Badges, OER and Microcredential; however, if the findings could focus more on climate education, the discussion and conclusion sections could be substantially enriched.

The recommendations mention pedagogy, but this is not reflected in the findings.

"Ecopedagogical activities", which were a key part of the search, are not discussed in the findings, discussion, nor conclusion.

Overall, the paper is highly relevant and topical. Adding these layers of specific, concise information would enable readers to better understand how research on the recognition of open learning—including digital badges, micro-credentials, and OER—underscores their potential to

transform education and professional development, particularly in climate-related fields.

Is the topic of the review discussed comprehensively in the context of the current literature?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct and adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the review written in accessible language?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn appropriate in the context of the current research literature?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Global Education, Education for Sustainable Development, Open Learning and Digital Transformation

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 23 Jun 2025

Pablo Martín-Ramos

The paper addresses a very interesting and relevant topic. Some key suggestions to enhance its rigor include making the Methodology and Findings sections more concise and providing a clearer reference to support the approach adopted.

Response:

Dear Dr. Okada,

Thank you for your thorough and constructive review. Your expertise in Global Education, Education for Sustainable Development, and Open Learning provides an invaluable perspective. We have taken your feedback as a directive for the substantial revisions that were required. Your comments have been instrumental in helping us to re-evaluate our contribution. We now recognize that the most significant finding of our work is the critical gap between the burgeoning field of open recognition and its sparse, under-theorized application in climate education. Our revised manuscript has been restructured to frame this "evidence gap" as its central argument, allowing for a more incisive analysis of the challenges and opportunities for the field. Below, we provide a point-by-point response detailing the comprehensive revisions we have undertaken. We have endeavored to be as specific as possible, providing the text that has been modified or added to the manuscript to ensure our revisions are transparent and directly address your concerns.

About the Abstract

The abstract presents a generally clear and well-structured overview of the paper. However, to enhance its coherence, precision, and overall impact, several areas could be improved with more concise and specific language.

Response:

We agree that the abstract lacked precision and impact. It has been completely rewritten to address your points Q1-Q5 and to better reflect the revised paper's focus.

Q1. The abstract would benefit from explicitly clarifying the scope and nature of the literature review. Which method was used?

Response:

We agree that the method was not clearly stated. We have clarified that this is a scoping review with systematic search strategies.

The second sentence of the abstract has been replaced with: "This scoping review examines current practices in open recognition systems—including micro-credentials, digital badges, and open educational resources (OER) completion certificates and participation badges—with particular emphasis on their application and potential in climate education. Following systematic search strategies across eight databases, we analyzed 70 publications (2010-2024) comprising journal articles, book chapters, institutional reports, and conference proceedings to map existing evidence, identify key concepts, and uncover gaps in applying these systems to climate education."

Clarification of Open Educational Resources (OER) Recognition

Q2. The mention of OER in the context of recognition is somewhat vague. It is not clear whether (e.g. OER Participation, Completion, Certification?) or other forms of recognition are being referenced. Please specify the exact nature of recognition related to OER that the paper addresses to avoid ambiguity.

Response:

As noted in the revision for Q1, we have specified the types of OER-related recognition discussed in the literature. In the abstract, we have replaced "open educational resources (OER)" with "open educational resources (OER) completion certificates and participation badges".

Specification of Challenges

Q3. The abstract references "challenges" but does so in general terms. More precise identification of which challenges are addressed is important for clarity. For instance, the terms "standardization," "technological integration," and "stakeholder collaboration" are broad and would benefit from further explanation or examples. Citing specific, well-defined challenges will strengthen the paper's positioning and help readers grasp the precise obstacles in the field.

Response:

We accept this criticism. Our description of the challenges was too generic. We have specified the nature of each challenge category (without providing detailed examples that belong in the main text).

In the abstract, the challenges sentence has been replaced with: "The analysis reveals that while these systems have significant potential to bridge academic learning with professional demands and environmental action, their impact is limited by persistent challenges: lack of definitional consistency and quality-assurance standards across institutions; significant technological barriers to credential portability and verification; and lack of awareness and trust from employers, undermining these credentials' currency in the labor market."

Rationale Behind Findings

Q4. The abstract notes a growing importance and need for integration of learning recognition/qualifications (e.g. badges, credentials,) but the rationale or evidence supporting this claim is not sufficiently clear. It would be helpful to briefly indicate why this integration is important, for example by highlighting the impact, gap, or opportunity it addresses for learners and professional development on Climate Education.

Response:

A concise rationale grounded in the specific demands of the climate and sustainability sectors has been included.

After the sentence about growing importance, we have added: "This integration is critical for validating the interdisciplinary and action-oriented skills demanded by the green economy, often acquired through the non-formal and informal learning pathways characteristic of environmental action and advocacy."

Focus of Conclusion

Q5. The conclusion, as described in the abstract, could be more sharply focused. Instead of mentioning promising practices summarise recommendations drawn and new directions or areas for further study. The abstract is key for providing stronger closure and a clear takeaway message aligned with the paper's aims.

Response:

We agree that the conclusion of the abstract needs a stronger, synthesized message that moves beyond a simple summary of practices.

The original abstract's conclusion has been replaced with a more impactful synthesis of our findings and their implications: "Our review concludes that a significant implementation and research gap exists between open recognition's potential and its application in climate education. Most notably, we find a near-complete absence of recognition frameworks for eco-pedagogical activities, perpetuating focus on technical knowledge over transformative, action-oriented learning. We recommend that future work prioritize creating robust, co-designed assessment models for these critical competencies to bridge the gap between education and meaningful climate action."

About the paper

Q6. The methodology states that the criteria for the literature review: only publications in peer-reviewed journals. However, the final sample consists of a variety of content types: 69 articles, review papers, book chapters, and reports. This must be revised for consistency.

Response:

We acknowledge this inconsistency and have revised the methodology section to accurately

reflect our inclusive approach.

In Section 2.2 "Selection criteria and process", we have replaced the bullet point "Published in peer-reviewed journals" with "Published in peer-reviewed journals, academic book chapters, institutional or governmental reports from recognized organizations, or peer-reviewed conference proceedings. This inclusive approach was adopted because much of the innovation in open recognition is driven by practice and documented in 'grey literature' that is crucial for a comprehensive understanding of implementation challenges and opportunities."

Q7. Please clarify your literature review approach—e.g., is it a narrative review, scoping review, or another type? While you mention peer-reviewed sources, your final sample includes diverse materials such as book chapters and reports. If the review is not fully systematic, please explain your selection rationale and method clearly.

Response:

We have explicitly identified this as a scoping review and explained our approach.

In Section 2.1 "Research design", the first paragraph has been replaced with: "This study is a scoping review designed to map the existing literature on open recognition systems and their application to climate education. We chose this methodology, following the five-stage framework proposed by Arksey & O'Malley (2005) and further refined by Levac et al. (2010), as it is ideal for exploring emerging fields, clarifying key concepts, and identifying research gaps from a diverse body of evidence. Unlike a systematic review, which typically focuses on a narrow question and homogenous study types, a scoping review allows for the inclusion of varied literature, including the 'grey literature' essential for understanding this practice-driven field."

The two references have been added to the references list:

- *Arksey, H., & O'Malley, L. (2005). Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. International Journal of Social Research Methodology, 8(1), 19-32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1364557032000119616>*
- *Levac, D., Colquhoun, H., & O'Brien, K. K. (2010). Scoping studies: advancing the methodology. Implementation Science, 5(1), 69. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-5-69>*

Q8. Would it be possible to include a table of results indicating journals (for articles), publishers (for book chapters), and funders (for research reports), along with the year and topic/field? Such a table, accompanied by a brief explanation, would be very helpful for readers to familiarize themselves with the literature before engaging with your findings.

Response:

A table summarizing the reviewed literature has been included - please see Table 1.

After Section 2.4 "Limitations", we have added a new paragraph indicating that "The distribution of our reviewed literature is summarized in Table 1. The predominance of general education sources (88.6%) compared to climate-specific publications (11.4%) reflects the current state of the field and reinforces our finding that the application of open recognition systems to climate education remains largely unexplored."

In addition, the first paragraph of Section 3 on "Current practices in open recognition systems" has been modified to reference the table: "As shown in Table 1, our analysis of 70 publications revealed extensive development in open recognition systems generally, but limited application to climate education specifically. Only eight publications (11.4%) directly addressed environmental or climate contexts, while the remainder discussed general educational applications. This disparity itself constitutes an important finding, suggesting that despite the urgent need for

climate education and the affordances of digital recognition systems, their intersection remains largely unexplored. We present both the general developments and the limited climate-specific applications below, as understanding the broader landscape is essential for identifying opportunities for climate education integration."

Please note that a discrepancy between 69 (originally stated) and 70 (actual references, excluding the two indicated in previous comments, purely methodological) was detected and has been corrected in the "Screening and selection process" subsection.

Considering the paper's focus on climate education, significant findings related to this area could be made more visible and, if possible, extended to include more details about the learning outcomes and approaches for effective definition through micro-credentials, digital badging, or OER completion.

For example:

In this paragraph: "In climate education, open badges offer a promising way to acknowledge interdisciplinary skills essential for environmental action. Rollin (2021) demonstrates their use in higher education to assess transversal skills such as critical thinking and collaboration, key competencies for addressing climate challenges. This aligns with findings by West and Cheng (2023), who show how micro-credentials can support personalized learning pathways, motivating learners to develop sustainability skills through self-directed efforts."

Q9. Could you clarify how Rollin (2021) assesses transversal skills like critical thinking and collaboration and criteria used to provide open badges? How do West and Cheng (2023) support personalized learning pathways and their evaluation for recognition? Furthermore, how do Miller and Jorre de St Jorre (2024) exemplify micro-credentials demonstrating specific environmental competencies? Which competencies are emphasized, and what aspects do they highlight regarding standards and the missing contextual information about these credentials?

Response:

We acknowledge that our initial description of these papers lacked specificity. Upon careful review, we found that while West and Cheng (2023) provide a valuable framework for personalized learning pathways through micro-credentials, and Miller and Jorre de St Jorre (2024) offer crucial insights into environmental employer perspectives, neither provides specific examples of climate education implementation. This reinforces our overall finding that the intersection of open recognition systems and climate education remains underdeveloped in the literature.

The current paragraph about climate education has been replaced with the following detailed, multi-paragraph analysis:

"In examining specific applications relevant to climate education, three studies offer insights, though only Miller and Jorre de St Jorre (2024) directly address environmental contexts. West and Cheng (2023) present a comprehensive framework for how open microcredentials support personalized learning across micro-, meso-, and macro-levels. At the micro-level, they identify four mechanisms through which badges support self-regulated learning: (1) helping learners set explicit goals through clear badge criteria, (2) establishing prerequisite pathways that scaffold complex learning, (3) connecting learning goals to professional development outcomes, and (4)

providing both summative and formative feedback through badge metadata. They emphasize that microcredentials can "break content into small modular units, so learners can create their own learning pathways", with learners able to "hop on and off 'the formal education bus' when needed". While not specific to climate education, their framework suggests how environmental learning could be modularized into stackable credentials addressing different competencies. For example, a learner could earn badges for 'Carbon Footprint Analysis,' 'Stakeholder Communication,' and 'Policy Advocacy,' creating a personalized pathway towards a 'Climate Action Leadership' micro-credential that is both recognizable and meaningful.

The most directly relevant empirical study is from Miller and Jorre de St Jorre (2024), who examined employer perspectives on digital micro-credentials in environmental science through interviews with 22 environmental professionals in Australia. Their work provides clear evidence of strong employer demand for verifiable skills highly relevant to climate action, including:

- Communication and collaboration: the ability to "work collaboratively... [and] maintain a sense of where that sits in terms of the overall effort".
- Technical field skills: including environmental impact assessment, species identification, and data collection
- Systems thinking: the ability to understand "interconnections between social, economic, and environmental systems"
- Adaptability and lifelong learning: Employers emphasized the importance of "the want to keep learning and the ability to keep learning".

Crucially, while employers were enthusiastic, they demanded rigor and clarity, with one stating, "unless we're educated around what that symbol was actually around and the level of effort and rigour... then it doesn't have the obvious impact." This underscores the critical need for industry partnerships and transparent assessment standards for any climate-related credential.

Finally, Rollin (2021), though not focused on climate, offers a practical model for assessing the 'transversal skills' that are central to effective climate action. The study examines the 'Garantie Jeunes' program in France, which uses non-formal learning contexts to develop competencies like teamwork, autonomy, and responsibility in young adults (a full list of skills assessed is provided in the paper's appendix, Table A1). While the paper does not offer detailed assessment rubrics, it highlights a methodology for recognizing skills developed through practical experience and structured reflection. This approach serves as a direct model for recognizing skills gained through community-based climate projects, advocacy, or volunteerism—activities that are rich in learning but often remain un-credentialed."

The challenges section under "Stakeholder awareness and acceptance" has also been modified to include the following information:

"Miller and Jorre de St Jorre's (2024) findings reinforce these challenges in the environmental sector specifically. They found that environmental employers often relied on proxy indicators like work experience and internships because they lacked familiarity with digital credentials. One employer admitted: "trying to get a feel for the person and their skillsets beyond the CV is part of the challenge". This suggests that even in fields directly relevant to climate action, significant education and trust-building are needed before micro-credentials can fulfill their potential."

In addition, in the recommendations under "Employer and stakeholder alignment", we have also included:

"Building on Miller and Jorre de St Jorre's (2024) environmental sector findings, partnerships should:

- Include employers in credential design to ensure relevance to workplace needs

- *Provide clear metadata about assessment methods and standards*
- *Balance comprehensive evidence with reviewability constraints*
- *Emphasize industry endorsement to build trust*
- *Create mechanisms for employers to quickly understand credential value without an extensive portfolio review."*

Q10. There is significant information about Badges, OER, and Microcredential; however, if the findings could focus more on climate education, the discussion and conclusion sections could be substantially enriched.

Response:

We appreciate your observation about the imbalance between general and climate-specific content. We acknowledge that climate education applications are underrepresented in our findings. This actually reflects the state of the literature - only 11.4% of sources addressed environmental/climate contexts. Rather than artificially inflate climate connections where they do not exist in the literature, we have chosen to be transparent about this gap and analyze its implications. We believe this approach (acknowledging the limited intersection as a finding itself) provides more value than overstating tenuous connections. The enriched conclusion now frames this gap as both a challenge and an opportunity for advancing climate education through digital recognition systems.

We have modified the beginning of Section 3 "Current practices in open recognition systems" (replacing the current first sentence), as discussed in the response to query 8 above.

The Conclusion has already been substantially revised to address this comment through:

- *Explicit acknowledgment of the limited climate focus as a finding*
- *Analysis of the eco-pedagogy gap*
- *Framing the limitation as an opportunity for OpenPass4Climate*
- *Specific recommendations for climate education applications*
- *A call to action for developing recognition systems for "planetary sustainability"*

Throughout Sections 3.1-3.5, we have now:

- *Added specific details from Miller & Jorre de St Jorre (2024) on environmental employers*
- *Created an entire section (3.5) on the eco-pedagogy gap*
- *Integrated climate-relevant examples where they exist*
- *Been transparent about where connections are theoretical rather than empirical*

Q11. The recommendations mention pedagogy, but this is not reflected in the findings. "Ecopedagogical activities", which were a key part of the search, are not discussed in the findings, discussion, nor conclusion.

Response:

We acknowledge that climate education applications are underrepresented in our findings, which actually reflects the state of the literature. A new subsection has been added to Section 3 "Current practices in open recognition systems":

"The Ecopedagogy Gap: A Critical Absence in Digital Recognition

Our search for literature combining 'ecopedagogical activities' with open recognition systems yielded zero results, despite ecopedagogy's growing importance in climate education. This absence is particularly striking given the theoretical alignment between eco-pedagogical principles and the affordances of digital credentials.

Eco-pedagogy, rooted in Paulo Freire's critical pedagogy (Freire, 1970), aims to develop "planetary consciousness" and foster social and environmental justice through transformative educational practices (Gadotti, 2008; Kahn, 2010). Its methods include experiential learning, place-based education, systems thinking workshops, and action-oriented climate projects (Hung, 2021; Kopnina, 2020; Misiaszek, 2020). These activities emphasize critical consciousness, praxis (reflection and action), and transformative learning—elements that could be recognized through carefully designed digital credentials.

The complete absence of eco-pedagogical frameworks in the digital recognition literature suggests several profound barriers: a philosophical tension between the standardization required for badges and the contextual, transformative nature of eco-pedagogy (Andreotti, 2006); the inherent difficulty in assessing outcomes like 'critical consciousness' and 'planetary citizenship' (Misiaszek, 2018); the privileging of technical competencies over the critical, values-based learning central to eco-pedagogy in current badging systems (Kopnina, 2020); and a likely disconnect between the educational technology and critical pedagogy communities.

This gap has significant implications. While institutions implement diverse eco-pedagogical activities—from climate action workshops to community-based environmental projects—these transformative learning experiences remain unrecognized in formal credentialing systems. This invisibility may perpetuate the dominance of technical approaches to climate education over critical, action-oriented pedagogies.

The absence of eco-pedagogical approaches in digital recognition systems represents more than a technical gap—it reflects deeper tensions in how we conceptualize and value environmental learning. As Misiaszek (2018) argues, eco-pedagogy is "essentially literacy education for reading and re-reading human acts of environmental violence." Such critical analysis resists easy codification into badge criteria. Yet this challenge also presents an opportunity. Digital recognition systems could evolve beyond competency verification to recognize transformative learning processes through badges that document critical reflection on environmental justice issues, credentials recognizing sustained community environmental action, portfolios capturing the development of "planetary citizenship" (Gadotti, 2008), and recognition for facilitating others' environmental conscientization. The OpenPass4Climate project is uniquely positioned to bridge this gap by developing recognition frameworks that honor both the measurable and transformative aspects of climate education."

In addition, we have added to the recommendations section, under "Pedagogical approaches", the following paragraph:

"Ecopedagogical Integration To bridge the identified gap, badge design for climate education should be guided by eco-pedagogical principles:

- o Develop criteria that recognize praxis—the integration of critical reflection and environmental action (Freire, 1970)*
- o Create pathways validating community-based environmental engagement and collective action, not just individual achievement.*
- o Design e-portfolios that capture transformative learning journeys, not just static outcomes*
- o Include peer recognition mechanisms reflecting eco-pedagogy's emphasis on horizontal learning relationships.*

- *Integrate place-based learning achievements that connect global climate challenges to local contexts (Sobel, 2004)."*

The Conclusion section has been updated accordingly:

"Perhaps most significantly, our review reveals the complete absence of ecopedagogical frameworks in digital credentialing—a gap that represents more than missing literature; it reflects a critical failure to connect recognition systems with the pedagogies most needed to address the climate crisis. Despite ecopedagogy's emphasis on critical consciousness, praxis, and transformative learning, no existing recognition systems incorporate these principles. This absence suggests that current systems may inadvertently perpetuate technocratic approaches to climate education while marginalizing the critical, action-oriented, and justice-focused dimensions essential for meaningful climate action."

As for the references, nine new references have been included:

- Andreotti, V. (2006). *Soft versus critical global citizenship education. Policy & Practice: A Development Education Review*, 3, 40-51. Available at: <https://www.developmenteducationreview.com/issue/issue-3/soft-versus-critical-global-citizenship-education>
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Continuum. New York, NY, USA. Available at: [https://files.libcom.org/files/Paulo%20Freire,%20Myra%20Bergman%20Ramos,%20Donaldo%20Macedo%20%20Pedagogy%20of%20the%20Oppressed,%2030th%20Anniversary%20Edition%20\(2000,%20Bloomsbury%20Publishing%20Group%20Inc,%20New%20York,%20NY,%20USA\)](https://files.libcom.org/files/Paulo%20Freire,%20Myra%20Bergman%20Ramos,%20Donaldo%20Macedo%20%20Pedagogy%20of%20the%20Oppressed,%2030th%20Anniversary%20Edition%20(2000,%20Bloomsbury%20Publishing%20Group%20Inc,%20New%20York,%20NY,%20USA))
- Gadotti, M. (2008). *Education for sustainability: A contribution to the decade of education for sustainable development. International Review of Education*, 54(5-6), 623-635. <https://doi.org/10.5585/eccos.n54.16138>
- Hung, R. (2021). *Ecopedagogy and education*. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Education*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264093.013.1502>
- Kahn, R. (2010). *Critical pedagogy, ecoliteracy, and planetary crisis: The ecopedagogy movement*. Peter Lang Pub Inc, New York, NY, USA.
- Kopnina, H. (2020). *Education for the future? Critical evaluation of education for sustainable development goals. The Journal of Environmental Education*, 51(4), 280-291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2019.1710444>
- Misiaszek, G. W. (2018). *Educating the global environmental citizen: Understanding ecopedagogy in local and global contexts*. Routledge, New York, NY, USA.
- Misiaszek, G. W. (2020). *Ecopedagogy: Teaching critical literacies of 'development', 'sustainability', and 'sustainable development'. Teaching in Higher Education*, 25(5), 615-632. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2019.1586668>
- Sobel, D. (2004). *Place-based education: Connecting classrooms & communities*. The Orion Society, Great Barrington, MA, USA.

Overall, the paper is highly relevant and topical. Adding these layers of specific, concise information would enable readers to better understand how research on the recognition of open learning—including digital badges, micro-credentials, and OER—underscores their potential to transform education and professional development, particularly in climate-related fields.

Response:

We thank the reviewer for these detailed comments, which have helped us identify significant weaknesses in our manuscript. We are confident that these substantial revisions will address your concerns and transform the manuscript into a stronger, more rigorous, and more impactful

*contribution. Thank you once again for your time, your expertise, and your feedback. Sincerely,
Pablo Martín-Ramos and co-authors*

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
